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Mentoring in Leadership: Appraising Samuel-Saul's Relationship

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Abstract

Pastoral office is inherently a leadership office as it involves guiding and shepherding a congregation, community or an individual towards spiritual and moral wellbeing. Pastors as leader have a crucial role to play in fostering sense of unity, provision of support, and nurturing growth in the body of Christ. This leadership extends beyond traditional organisational structure but focuses on the total development of an individual in the community of faith. In the pastoral context, leadership is not solely limited to administrative duty but also involves guidance and care for individuals. By the very nature of their task, pastors are meant to be mentors who offer counsel and provide source of inspiration to their mentees. Their leadership style analysis empathy, compassion and deep understanding of the need of their protégé. In this wise, the effectiveness of a pastor as a leader is measured by their ability to connect with people on a personal level by helping them navigate the challenges of life. Samuel, by circumstances, becomes the spiritual leader to Saul. In a hitherto-new office of monarchy, Saul needs a mentor. This study uses Textual, and descriptive methods of analysis, in examining Samuel and Saul's relationship in the Biblical text. It finds that Samuel fails in mentorship due, perhaps, to personal grudges. It concludes that every spiritual leader is, after all, a fallible being. Therefore, it recommends among other things that spiritual leaders should be weary of personal sentiment in discharging their roles.

Introduction

For most Bible believing individuals (Christians or Jews), King Saul's failure is as a result of divine displeasure and rejection (1 Sam 16:1). But be that as it may, Saul's tragedy reveals a mentorship flaw on the part of Samuel, Israel's first king maker. But the towering figure of Samuel in the scripture shields this weakness of Samuel from view. It is worth noting from here that the intent of this study is neither to cast aspersion on Samuel nor to diminish his positive roles in Saul's' career. In point of fact, Samuel gives Saul dignified reception at Zuph (1 Sam. 9:22-24), announces divine choice of Saul (1 Sam. 9:27-10:1), and even has a discussion with him (1 Sam. 9:25). However, certain flaws are evident in his dealings with Saul and much can be learnt from it about mentorship. By divine providence, Samuel was in position to guide King Saul. But for certain reasons this was not always the case. Maxwell says leaders usually fail to develop other leaders either on account of their lack of training or because they have wrong attitudes about allowing and encouraging others to come alongside them (Maxwell, 1995). The latter seems to be the case of Samuel as would be discussed.

The often-overlooked mortal error of Samuel may be due in part to the 'Touch not my anointed' syndrome which makes some people believe that spiritual leaders are to be absolved of any error whatsoever; or as a result of the misconstrued intent of Jesus in saying "Do not judge..." (Matt. 7:1). This paper briefly reviews Samuel's mentorship inadequacy in early monarchical narratives with a view to correcting the belief that spirituality forecloses mistakes.

What is Mentorship?

A wide variety of definitions to capture the meaning of mentorship may be available with each reflecting different roles and intents behind mentoring. However, some things that are common to most of these definitions are an acknowledgement of the reciprocity, and one-to-one nature of the relationship between a more experienced and a less experienced individual for the purpose of personal and professional development. Canadian Coalition for Global Health Research reports some definitions two of which are offered here for consideration: Mentoring is a "dynamic and non-competitive nurturing 'process'...that promotes independence, autonomy, and self-actualization in the protégé while fostering a sense of pride and fulfillment, support and continuity in the mentor." "Mentoring occurs when a senior person (the mentor) in terms of age and experience undertakes to provide information, advice, and emotional support for a junior person (the protégé) in a relationship lasting over an extended period of time and marked by substantial emotional commitment by both parties" (Canadian Coalition, 2007, pp.6-7) World Education Services puts it thus; "A mentorship is a relationship between two people where the individual with more experience, knowledge, and connections is able to pass along what they have learnt to a more junior individual within a certain field. The more senior individual is the mentor, and the more junior individual is the mentee (Center for Health, 2003).

A United Nation handbook on mentoring says important traits like empathy, curiosity, authenticity and the ability to connect and impart trust are among those things a mentor should have. It says further that "Research shows that these are more important than the professional skills a mentor may have" (Together, p.5).

Mentoring is crucial for leadership development as it provides opportunity for prospective future leaders to see transformational behaviours in action. Wofford reports Gary Yukl's guidelines for mentoring. He says mentors are expected to have interest in the development of their mentees, serve as role models to them, help them identify skill deficiencies and guide them to overcome the deficiencies by giving career advice among other points (Wofford, 2004).

The Core of Mentorship is Mentorship

Mentorship is a phenomenon that has similarity with some other transformational relationship. As such, mentorship, discipleship, and modeling may have been used interchangeably sometimes. While some believe that they can be used interchangeably, others are of the opinion that they are different and should not be so used. Though it is out of the scope of this article, to give delineating marks of each of the terms, they seem vastly different and may not be used *substitutably*.

A number of features distinguish mentorship from other interactions between more experienced and less experienced individuals in organisational or institutional settings. Consequently, mentorship can, but does not always, exist in relationships between teacher and student or between professionals at varying levels of a bureaucratic or academic hierarchy. The relationship grows over time and is deliberate, purposeful and interpersonal.

Just as there are different definitions, so are types of mentorship. Mentorship can be spontaneous or formal, direct or indirect, and short or long-term (Canadian Coalition, 2007). Perhaps the most closely aligned with our definitions of mentorship is direct mentorship. Here, direct relationship results between two individuals, often a more experienced member in an organisation or group (the 'mentor') and a less experienced one in the same organisation or group (the 'mentee' or 'protégé'). It can also result from supervisor-student relationship.

Collegial mentorship integrates the characteristic of friendship into the traditional definition of the relationship of mentorship. This type of mentoring acknowledges and promotes the development of a personal, supportive relationship between mentor and protégé. The starting point may be through friendship or professional contact and not due to professional needs. For instance, a junior faculty member may develop collegial mentoring relationships with more senior faculty. Student-supervisor relationship is another example of collegial relationship, which creates opportunities for collaboration in research beyond the thesis or dissertation. Indirect mentoring does not involve mentor-mentee direct contact. It is the result of intentional efforts from a mentor to be available to junior members of an organization intending mentees.

Formal and informal mentorship differ in the way the relationship is initiated, how mentor and mentee are identified, and the focus, length, and structure of the relationship. Formal mentoring evolves from structured, organised programmes or assigned roles within an organisation. On the other hand, informal mentoring develops through mutual identification—the mentor believes in the mentee's potential and the mentee selects mentors they consider role models.

Linda Phillips-Jones mentoring expert and author describes four basic mentoring skills which are: Active listening, Building trust, Determining goals/Capacity building and Encouraging/Inspiring (Center for Health, 2003). According to her, not only does active listening establish rapport it also creates a positive, accepting environment which gives

room for open communication. By listening actively, a mentor comes to ascertain the protégé's interests and needs. As regards trust building, one will increase trust by keeping conversations and other communications with a protégé confidential, honoring scheduled meetings and calls, consistently showing interest and support, and by being honest with him/her. Capacity building will involve various assistance and knowledge impartation. But she wraps it up by maintaining that "giving encouragement is the mentoring skill most valued by protégés" (Mentoring Guide, 2003, p.4). This can be achieved by commenting favorably on their accomplishments; assuring them of belief in their capacity to grow; responding to their frustrations and challenges with words of support, understanding, encouragement and possibly praise. Mentors may even describe their own experiences, mistakes, and successes all in a bit to provide proper mentorship.

From the foregoing, a mentor helps protégés advance within their chosen career and connects them with opportunities that they might not have otherwise had access to. They do this by sharing their knowledge, helping their protégé identify prospects and opportunities in their path. Potentially, mentors can open doors for their mentee when the time comes. Thus, mentorship is a prized instrument for turning one's vision into reality.

It is expected of mentors to give guidance and counsel to their mentees, helping them build a successful career or gain a strong foothold within a certain organisation. Because it is a relational affair, a mentor typically (but not in every instance) has one mentee at a time and focuses on shaping the trajectory of their career life. The experience affects the amount of psychosocial support, career guidance, role modeling and communication that occurs in the mentoring relationships in which the protégés and mentors engaged. Mentorship is a mutually beneficial relationship. The mentors gain because they are able to lead the future generation in an area they care about and ensure that best practices are passed along; in the same vein, the mentees benefit because they prove that they are ready to take the next step in their career and can receive the extra help needed to make that advancement. Across different disciplines, mentorship is recognised both in academic and practice settings as an important contributor to capacity building within organisations and among individuals.

In secular mentoring, attention is given to professional development, improvement of leadership skills, or guiding people into skills they want to grow in. Not only are these valid reasons to seek mentorship, they are also important. But in biblical mentorship (especially the Old Testament), mentoring entails more than self-improvement, personal development or merely passing on knowledge about God. It involves showing people how to love and serve God. It is about helping an individual grow in obedience to the requirement of the law. The concept finds poignant expression, at least, as old as the book of Deuteronomy:

Hear, O Israel: The Lord our God, the Lord is one. Love the Lord your God with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your strength. These commandments that I give you today are to be on your hearts. Impress them on your children. Talk about them when you sit at home and when you walk along the road, when you lie down and when you get up. Tie them as symbols on your hands and bind them on your foreheads. Write them on the doorframes of your houses and on your gates. (Deut. 6:4-9)

God provides a biblical format of mentoring within the family to ensure that faith in the one true and living God would be passed from generation to generation.

It can be generally assumed that a good mentee is a product of good a good mentor in keeping with popular saying that “like begets like.” It should be noted that some mentors may have character flaws and weak leadership but nonetheless provide good mentoring. Instances abound where a not-too-good mentor produces a good mentee (Jacob-Joseph, Eli-Samuel) and where acclaimed good leader produces a flawed protégé (e.g. Elisha-Gheazi). But one clear fact from biblical examples is that many great biblical leaders were mentored.

Leaders in Old Testament and Influence of Mentorship

Though arguably, there are no better known leaders in the Old Testament than Moses and David. Other notable ones include Joshua, Joseph, Samuel, Elisha and Esther. All these aforementioned individuals have remarkable achievements in their leadership. But also notable about them, is the fact that each of them enjoys some sort of mentorship under certain individuals: Joseph under his father Jacob (Gen. 37:2), Moses under Jethro (Exo.2:16-22; 18:1-27), Joshua under Moses (Exo.32:17-18, Num.27:18-23, Deut. 34:9), Samuel under Eli (1 Sam. 3:1-9), David under Samuel (ISam. 16:13; 19:18), Elisha under Elijah (II Kings 3:11) and Esther under Mordecai (Esther 2:7,10).

This reveals a fact that every great leader has frailty and human failings which are helped by some mentorship. Ted Engstrom notes that a close scrutiny of leaders mentioned in the Bible, indicates that majority of them at one time or another experienced failure. Many of them, according to him, have their failure in marked ways but they later succeed because they never grovel in the dust (Engstrom, 1976). For dearth of space, three of these leaders are briefly examined: Moses, Samuel and Elisha.

Moses

Moses, the great leader and lawgiver of Israel, is born an Israelite into slavery in Egypt. As indicated earlier, someone says apart from Jesus, in Moses we have the greatest and best example of leadership found in the Bible (Amanzee, nd, p. 75). By divine providence, he is raised in the palace of Pharaoh King of Egypt (Exo. 2:10). But Moses,

aware of his origin, decides to help his people. Undoubtedly destined to be a leader of his people, Moses starts out by an attempt to settle dispute between two Israelites (Exo. 2:13-14). Of course, at the outset, his people do not understand his role in their midst (cf. Act 7:23-25). They ask “who made you a ruler and judge over us?” Although, Moses receives much direction and encouragement for the herculean task ahead of him, and on countless occasions demonstrates fabulous leadership qualities, he nonetheless, begins his career as a statesman when he attains the age of eighty (Engstrom, 1976). That is pretty well after having been mentored by his father-in-law. Philomena Amanzee states that at this time, which she prefers to describe as God’s tutorship of Moses, he comes out of the training being kind, considerate, and compassionate. He also acquires abilities for organization, administration, law, and sound judgment (Amanzee, p. 7).

Obviously, Moses is an ambitious and zealous leader who desires the emancipation of his people from the clutch of Egyptian enslavement. Having been raised in the palace, the leadership (or perhaps *rulership*) tendency in him is well formed. His drive and zeal make him break the tablets (Exo.32:19), earn him jealous rebukes from siblings (Num. 12:1-2), and other detractors (Num. 16:1-3). But despite his zeal and drive, he is said to be extremely meek (Num. 12:3). This is in sharp contrast to the Moses in Exodus 2:11-12 killing an Egyptian. What makes the difference is mentorship.

Moses departs Egypt at age 40 and returns at 80. He lives with a Midianite priest whose daughter he marries. One clear indication of his mentorship is the visit of Jethro (Exo 18) where he comes to see his mentee demonstrate his skill of leadership. Observing yet another impropriety in Moses’ administration of his leadership, Jethro offers some instructions which Moses follows. Thus, it is reasonable to conclude that moderation that comes to Moses’ leadership is a result of mentorship.

Elisha

Elisha is described as one who used to pour water into the hand of Elijah (II Kings 3:11). He becomes Elijah’s protégé towards the end of Ahab’s reign (I Kings 19:19-21). Elijah is still active until after the death of Ahaziah. Thus, Elisha’s ministry spans the reigns of Kings Joram, Jehu and Jehoahaz. He dies during the reign of king Jehoash after about fifty years of public ministry which certainly involves leadership. He dies a revered national figure whose exploits are proudly rehearsed (Martin, 1986).

Elisha is renowned for his great miraculous acts, leadership and interpersonal relations. But his great success does not just come about. He is a man of sharp focus, unrelenting determination and staunch commitment to his mentor. Apart from Moses, hardly is there anyone in the Old Testament that performed more miraculous acts than the duo of Elijah and Elisha. Judging by this common denominator, one can rightly conclude that Elisha is well groomed by Elijah in the ‘art’ of waiting on God. Warren W. Wiersbe

(2003) notes that from the outset of Elisha's ministry, he demonstrates himself to be a worker of miracles like Elijah his master and predecessor. He opens the Jordan River, crosses on dry land, and then he purifies the water at Jericho. Apart from this, one feels that Elisha's 'harsh' dealing with the young men of Bethel (II Kgs 2:23-25) as well as Gheazi (II Kgs 5:25-27) reflects the nature of his mentor who deals with reprobate prophets I Kgs 18:40 and calls down fire on unruly soldiers II Kgs 1:10, 12.

Samuel

More than any other mentor-mentee relationship in the Old Testament, Eli-Samuel mentorship differs significantly in that Samuel starts from a young age. Samuel serves before the Lord under the Eli's guidance a time when God speak less often to His people. The spiritual leaders are corrupt, and God's voice is scares. But with Samuel in place, God changes the situation and speaks His prized word to a young boy who would be about twelve years old then (Wiersbe, 2003). While spiritual laxity is prevalent and the cherished law of God is dishonoured especially by the sons of Eli, the Biblical text still reveals Eli's close relationship with Samuel in a manner that demonstrates mentor-mentee rapport: the boy ministers before the Lord under Eli (3:1); he runs to Eli when a voice calls, thinking it is Eli's. This shows he is closer to the place Eli is sleeping than Eli's sons.

The most instructive demonstration of mentorship is when The Lord calls Samuel. The Lord calls him four times (1 Sam 3:4,6,8,10), and the first three times, Samuel thinks it is Eli calling him. He has never heard God's voice, so he does not know how to answer. Eli is discerning enough to recognize that it is God speaking to the boy, so he tells him how to respond. The young Samuel is helped by his elderly mentor who, at the time, is a dying light but bright enough to light Samuel's candle. Another notable thing is that Eli tells Samuel to say "Speak, Lord, for your servant is listening" (1 Sam 3:9, NIV) but Samuel instead says "Speak, for your servant is listening" (1 Sam 3:10, NIV), and leaves out the word, "Lord". This may be because he does not yet have a personal knowledge of the Lord he could not know whose voice it is. By the time Samuel later reports to Eli, Eli reiterated the fact that it is the Lord speaking: *He is the Lord...* (1 Sam 3:18, NIV).

Eli's choice of sleeping in the tabernacle precinct may be in keeping with The Ancient Near Eastern practice for incubation dream (Walton, et'al, 2000). It was a belief in the ancient world that a person sleeping in the temple or its precincts may become privy to divine plans. Some would in fact perform certain rituals and spend the night in the temple so as to receive such revelation. This process is known as incubation. 'In early literature kings such as Naram-Sin and Gudea sought information through incubation' (Walton, et'al, 2000) Samuel may simply be performing his regular duties and clearly has no expectation of revelation of any sort, his experience however, would be

understood in light of the common association between temple and revelation. This is a practice he most certainly imbibes from Eli his mentor.

Can Leaders be Mentored?

The above pertinent question, if reframed, would be “are leaders born or made?” for decades, this throbbing question has been asked both in religious and secular organisations. Scholars have over the years offered arguments stating that effective leaders emerge both from nurture of parents and from random choices of genetics. It is maintained by this position that leadership is largely formed before one graduate from high (secondary) school. A group of other scholars hold that effective leadership can be modeled in the years of adulthood (Wofford, 2004).

While hereditary and life experience play key roles in forming leadership ability an individual because leaders are expected to have some minimum level of intelligence, energy and personal appeal; effective leadership can be developed. Wofford reports the finding of a research done by Barling, Weber and Kelloway (Barling et al., 1996). They trained about twenty branch managers of one of Canada’s largest banks on ‘an effective and transforming leadership behaviours.’ In the research, they found out that training resulting in leadership change, brought about positive effects which produced better financial income of the banks (Wofford, 2004). Two other studies by Kilpatrick, Locke, Howell and Frost (Kilpatrick et al., 1996) further buttress the point. They found out that training increases the use of transforming leadership behaviours as well as leader’s effectiveness. Engstrom also says that for centuries, it has been assumed that leadership is inherited or passed from generation to generation, meaning “leaders were born-not made.” But following the overthrow of feudal system by a new burst of freedom in Europe due to the Renaissance, concept of leadership took a new shape. It is now seen that leaders can be trained and developed. Focus shifts to a person’s personality and skill which can be latent, waiting to be developed (Engstrom, 1976).

In biblical accounts, a number of individuals are trained for places of leadership even though they have a sure call from God. Best of these examples, perhaps, would be the disciples of Jesus Christ who receive training from Him (Jesus). During the Old Testament in the days of Samuel, a ‘school of prophets’ was set up to train the prophets (I Sam 18:19-20). Apparently, David no doubt seeks refuge here when fleeing from King Saul. Similarly, during Elijah and his protégé Elisha, such schools are located at Gilgal, Bethel and elsewhere (II Kings 2:1; 4:38; 6:1).

Jewish tradition has it that these schools trained persons to the office of prophets during Israel’s long history. The schools also served as forerunner to the Jewish Later Rabbinic centres in the postexilic era (Engstrom, 1976). Engstrom further maintains that these schools are meant to develop, train and educate people in leadership. Therefore, it is right to say that from biblical witnesses, leaders are made. Other Bible narratives and

events demonstrate the need and justification for development of an individual's gift in order to place them in positions of leadership which is what mentorship is all about. Moses, for instance, mentored Joshua. Seeing his potential, Moses groomed him to become an undisputed and enviable leader.

Samuel and Saul

When appraising the life of any man of God, it should be born in mind that they are human beings who are only privileged to have the divine mandate and calling to the nobler task of intermediary between the divine and human interfaces (Heb. 5:1). As such, the human failings and frailties are just as much to be expected of them. Denying this fact or attempting to shield it is a rude attempt to exchange humanity for divinity.

The summation above is very apt in apprising Samuel's action or inactions against Saul in Early monarchy in Israel. But briefly on Samuel, he occupies a very honourable position among the ancient Jews as revealed by many historical portrayal of his person. The only leader in Israel who occupied the three notable positions of prophet, priest and judge is Samuel. Provan, Long, and Longman describe him as transitional figure; being the last of the judges, successor of Eli the priest, and the prophet of the Lord (Provan et al, 2003). Among the ancient Israelite leaders, starting from Moses through Samuel and to the end of Biblical history, there is no one who held all these three positions. Not even Moses the lawgiver of Israel and greatest of their prophets was a high priest. He was only a judge and prophet. He is regarded as national leader second in rank to Moses as he revitalises the lost political and spiritual hopes of the people of Israel like Moses (Jensen, 1980). Even his role in military involvement is somewhat attested. While some contest this, Joseph Blenkinsopp (1983) sees no reason to deny him diversity of prophetic, political and military roles.

With this towering credential of Samuel, he was one that leaders expected to leave behind great leaders properly mentored. King Saul, being the immediate next in national leadership to Samuel, should be someone to enjoy this mentorship the most. But this is not the case. Samuel is an experienced leader and one who enjoyed mentorship. Saul, on the other hand, seems not only to be ignorant but also uninterested in leadership (1 Sam 9: 1ff; 10:21). So, when providence thrusts leadership on Saul, he doubtlessly needs a shoulder to rest on. The mark of true leadership is that someone is following. Saul has Samuel to look up to but Samuel provides him the needed training in leadership.

Saul has every reason to look up to Samuel for guidance. First, Samuel is a leader of great esteem and vast experience. Having led Israel from his youth to old age (12:2), and gaining national reputation for being a transformational leader; such a person would naturally attract mentees. Secondly, Samuel is the one that declares the divine choice of Saul to him (Saul). If then God chooses him through Samuel, it is reasonable that Saul

would need his guidance in matter of administration of his office. As such, mentor-mentee relationship should ensue. Thirdly, Saul's office is political and that of Samuel is spiritual. Because of the theocratic state of ancient Israel, a synergy between the two office holders is of necessity. Samuel, being older, would therefore need to provide guidance or better still mentoring to the younger fellow. But the narrative shows a mentoring flaw on the part of Samuel as indicated below.

Samuel's criticism of Saul: The Bible records few meetings between Samuel and Saul: His anointing (9:26-10:1), public presentation (10:17-25; 14-15), after Philistine battle at Michmash (13:5-15) and after destroying the Amalekites (15:1-29). After the anointing and public presentation, the scripture tells that Samuel and Saul meet again during the battle at Michmash; and after the battle against the Amalekites. In each of the instances, Saul is heavily criticised and tongue-lashed by Samuel. Saul is only a new king given instruction by his superior. Bruce Birch (1998) states that Chapter 13 of 1Samuel is a narrative of Saul's external conflict with the Philistines, and internal conflicts with Samuel. He declares that Saul does not succeed in overcoming either of these conflicts and is eventually brought to a tragic end by these conflicts. In fact, the text of 1Samuel 13 presents with challenges. It is unlikely that the instruction given in (10:8) is what Samuel charged Saul of not obeying. Laurent Porter (1979) comments that the event in this chapter must have taken place considerably later, just as many scholars too. One fact is that Samuel does not retreat into privacy after making Saul the king. He continues to act publicly and watching how kingship is executed. He issues a command which Saul is said to have disobeyed.

Many have misconstrued this episode to blame Saul for the whole problem. Samuel earlier makes arrangement to meet Saul at a certain time most likely to offer sacrifices and ask the Lord's blessing on the military venture. But as he does not show up, the few soldiers with Saul tremble and some start departing the war zone. Saul waits for seven days but Samuel does not arrive as promised. Was Samuel watching Saul to fail in the battles or seeking occasion against him to condemn monarchy? Is his arrival intentional or a coincidence? Has Saul done something wrong in offering the sacrifice? These are difficult questions to answer. But in sincerity, they implicate Samuel. Samuel is too angered as his brief question: 'What have you done?' indicates. Saul's explanation sounds as depredates the situation and perhaps as intimidating as Samuel's gesture is? Saul may have disobeyed some unknown divine instruction but Samuel's overreaction can only be read from the context of his hatred for monarchy and perceived persona rejection. Whatever the case, a mentor would have corrected a frustrated protégé in love and admitted his own wrong which Samuel does not do.

In the case of the destruction of the Amalekite, Saul's disobedience is obvious. But the befuddling things start from Samuel's introduction of the divine message (15:1). Ever since Samuel kissed Saul at the beginning of chapter 10, they never again share happy

moments. As a matter of fact, Samuel's general disposition to Saul has not been especially joyful. At the beginning of Chapter 15, the situation is not poised to change, in fact it would be worse. Samuel's first words indicate a stern mood. It begins with; 'I am the one the Lord sent to anoint you king over His people Israel; now listen' (15:1). This is a very odd introduction given that God disowned Saul's dynasty according to Samuel in Chapter 13. What then is the implication of Samuel's statement? By frontloading the pronoun "me" (rendered as 'I am the one' in NIV), the prophet sends a message to the king. He seems to be saying; 'I am the one in charge here even if you are the king and you must always take my word!' Samuel then announces divine judgment on Saul's action. But the tone raises questions about Samuel again. He said the king has refused the voice of the Lord, the Lord has also rejected him as king, but the king begs for forgiveness. It should be emphasised that Saul asks for forgiveness not for restoration as king but for the prophet to accompany him to worship God. Samuel refuses with a harsh negative response. In fact, he repeats essentially, his earlier lines: 'I will not return with you because you have rejected the word of the Lord and the Lord has rejected you from being king over Israel.' Peter (2015) opines that Samuel should have been more pastoral, and as a mentor of the first Israelite king, he should have offered counseling (p.89). Someone notes about the sternness of Samuel's reaction: 'is this the stern true prophet of the Lord declaring the Lord's word versus a sinner or is this a stern unrelenting prophet denouncing a rival?' (Miscall, 1986, p. 111). With this, it is hard to deny that Samuel has a lingering animosity towards Saul ever since his emergence on the scene. Here we see the poor ignorant and perhaps innocent king who is expecting succor and mentoring from a 'father' getting nothing but rebukes upon rebuke. No wonder he later becomes tarumatized and lapses into paranoia, and eventual suicide.

Samuel's desire to perpetuate a dynasty: Another point that demonstrates Samuel's failure in mentorship of Saul is his desire to perpetuate a dynasty. One of the reasons for the people's request to have monarchy is the failure of Samuel's children to live uprightly like their father (8:1-5). When age caught up with Samuel, he could no longer perform his duties especially the political cum judicial duties. So, he appoints his sons to take up the responsibilities. They however, lack the integrity and uprightness of their father. Apparently, his sons were appreciated no better than Eli's sons, and the people do not want them to take over. The elders of Israel lobby for a fundamental change. They demand for monarchy like other nations. When his sons fail as leaders, the elders see the system of discontinuity of the era of the judges returning. Their wish is to solve the problems of continuity, unifying the tribes, creation and maintenance of a professional army. Samuel may have thought of putting forward his sons for this position so that in future, his family line would enjoy the preeminence of producing the first king and perhaps maintain a dynasty. It is ironic that while the elders notify

Samuel about the spiritual and moral flaws of his sons as one of the bases for their request for a king (8:1-5), he still bring up their case in Saul's coronation more as an undying protest that even if monarchy is to be considered his family should have been given priority (12:1-2). If Samuel wants his family in monarchy, then, it won't be difficult to know why mentoring Saul would be hard to consider.

Aversion for monarchy: Through the years, the elders and the people of Israel have followed the political and spiritual leadership of Samuel without questioning in spite of the international political and military pressures. At this time, Samuel has grown old to the point that he cannot adequately lead the pole any longer. So, he appoints his sons. The once strenuous efforts of Samuel which youthful spirit, animated by piety and patriotism, had enabled him to make are perhaps no longer there. Thus, he sinks to phlegmatic indifference. Disabled by the infirmity of age from performing his duties, he delegates some to his son, but they by no means follow the step of the father.

The elders take advantage of this, coupled with desire to resolve their internal squabbles, and forge a national military apparatus, and approach Samuel to ask for monarchy. Samuel is immediately displeased by this (1 Sam. 8:6). While we may agree with Provan and other (2003) in their assertion: "that Israel's elders should so quickly in narrative time at least-demand 'a king to govern us like other nations' strike the attentive readers as a foreboding development" (p. 207). It is noticed that Samuel's reason for displeasure is not the same as that of Yhwh. The people want to be like other nations (something that they have been repeatedly warned against by God), but Samuel's concern is his own position!

The point is not that Israel was never to have a human monarch. Their traditions replete with anticipations for this (Gen. 17:6, 16; 35:11; Num. 24:7; 17-19; Deut 17:14-20). Also, given the fact that kingship was commonly practiced among their neighbours, it is perhaps less surprising that Israel should seek a king than that they have resisted doing so for so long. This event paints a different Samuel from what is popularly known him. He is seen here not displaying patriotism but self-seeking. He experiences demand for a king as a personal rejection. He prays to God perhaps to reject the people's request. God then tells him to heed the people's request (8:7). God has to repeat this to him to heed their demand, but that they should avoid idolatry. But in spite of God's explanation of the situation to Samuel; "it is not you they have rejected, but they have rejected me as their king" (8:7), God has to convince him over and over again to 'Listen to all that the people are saying to you...and give them a king' (8:7, 10, 22).

As can be seen, all the above show why Samuel felt no need to mentor Saul. Saul is trapped in the mist of battle of ambitious men. Men of Israel want a king Samuel wants a dynasty and Saul become the sacrificial lamb on the altar of their ambitions in the narrative sub-plot where he is presented as passive and yet blamed for whole scenario in the long run. More also, the fact that Samuel has corrupt sons is probably one of the

signs of a more complex character, with all the strengths and shortcomings common to well-developed personages in biblical literature. Since the narrator chooses to filter the narrative of the monarchy through the eye of Samuel, it behooves the readers to pay attention to such matter of Characterisation. Therefore, despite the overwhelming positive characterization of Samuel in the Monarchical narratives, his mentorship failure is evident not only in the case of Sal but also his sons.

Conclusion and Recommendation

From the foregoing, it is clear that Samuel is no doubt a great leader in Israel. Life application Study Bible notes that as a spiritual leader, he enjoys the uniqueness of filling different spiritual offices of judge, priest, prophet and counselor (NLT, 2007). He is so greatly used of God because of willing obedience to his parent's pledge to God, and desire to lean on God and to learn from Him. He champions great spiritual revolution, making word of God that was hitherto scarce, to be in abundance (cf. 1 Sam. 3:1; 19-21). He chooses a godly life despite growing among the ungodly children of Eli (I Sam.2:1-8); orchestrate national spiritual cleansing and revival (I Sam.7:3-6), and calls people to godliness (1 Sam. 12:14-23). Even the rise of prophetic institution in Israel has so much to do with him.

As regards his civil roles, Samuel is the first kingmaker, anointing the first two kings of Israel. He serves as a judge, and mediates in military venture (1 Sam. 7:7-12). Samuel may have had opportunity of mentoring many people. But from biblical text, the chance to mentor Saul and failure to do same is obviously a flaw in his intimidating good credential. While this does not make Samuel less spiritually and morally high personality, it does show that however spiritually great an individual is, the human part of them poses a great challenge and often faults their good nature. To this end; this recommends the followings:

- i. Leaders should try as much as possible to shun sentiment in the discharge of their leadership/mentorship roles
- ii. It should be recognised that every man of God is a human being prone to human failings. As such, they should not be overrated as superhuman in overall assessment of them.
- iii. Mentors should be conscious of the far-reaching influence of their actions/inactions on themselves and their protégé (Samuel weeps later, perhaps for his own mistake. Also, Saul internalises his constant criticism, develops negative self-image and later commits suicide).

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